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An Overview of Environmental Protection and Sustainable Development under : International Economic Law

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Abstract: This paper examines an overview of environmental protection and sustainable development worldwide under the umbrella of international economic law. In this paper we have addressed the environmental pollution growth along with the development of environmental protection laws for the last few years. It is clear that environmental protection and sustainable development 'has developed into too flexible theory to serve its essential purpose under the International Economic law. The paper analysis the theory of sustainable development that has determined the society to recognize and develop into responsive of the significance of ecological factors as well as of the function and services that the environment offers. Accordingly, it needs to be replaced with a basic title for the environmental movement. In this paper, we want to prove that sustainable development, Environmental protection must be considered in the determination of the line of action of International Economics law process. Specifically, the article will discuss various sources of implementation. Now it's the time that international community seriously think and reconsider their approach regarding environmental protection law under the international economic law, with today pressing global warming and environmental issues which is facing and great concern for all over the world.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Environment protection, Pollution, Economics law.

INTRODUCTION

Pollution is defined as "the degree of contamination of the physical and biological components of the land, ecosystem while the general ecological processes are badly affected."

The pollutant material is the substance or condition which contaminates air, water or soil; naturally happening substance or energy, but they are measured contaminated when higher than the natural level. The use of any rate of natural resources is more than the capacity of nature, which can pollute air, water and pollution to restore itself. "for example; As a result of rapid environmental consequences of carbon monoxide gas from automotive exhaust or sulfur dioxide emanate from factories, household products and chemicals, building materials etc., as a result of the rapid environmental impact of air, water and land resources, many incidents are being impure by toxic substances. And further pollutant, in which human health and ecosystem with severe health risk is obtained. Further comprehensive and exhaustive use of resources and energy has formed a cumulative force on the quality of local, regional and global ecosystems. Before a concerted effort was made to prevent the effect of pollution, environmental management could move slightly beyond the lines-fair tolerance in nature due to disposal of waste to avoid the disruptive local nuisance imagined in a short-term perspective. In the form of an exception, damage was identified, in cases where damage was determined to be unacceptable. As the speed of industrial activity accelerated and the understanding of cumulative effects increased, a pollution control pattern became a major perspective for environmental management.

Nations contain normally resisted international agreement, which are usually perceptible to shrink national sovereignty. Sovereignty means that every nation has associated duty not to intervene in the areas of exclusive jurisdiction of further nations. This theory of territorial autonomy does not co exist contentedly with an ecological order that consists of a biosphere of mutually dependent ecosystem, which do not be conventional to the synthetic protective territories between nations. Because of intimidation to autonomy, nations have resisted supportive to limit utilization of natural resources within their boundaries.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Environmental protection problems are a challenge without a single policy, but the combination of existing opportunities and increasing efficiency in all socio-economic areas of the countries will help solve the problem of resources and distribution. Environmental protection is currently a key area for international cooperation and regulations with a global or cross-border dimension. The persistence, purpose and provisional nature of environmental problems require global preventive action. (Lucretia Dogaru, 2013).

According to (Fuentes, X,2002) with the principles and concepts of international environmental law Progress in this field may have contributed to the tendency to leave conditional Ideas that are expanding and applying to a growing number of responsibilities Taken by states in the field of environmental protection. It is argued that environmental there has been a degree of protectionism at the expense of international economic law to make progress.

(Bennie and Boyle 1992) stated that prioritize Emerging issues and resist the international enforcement of environmental controls. As a outcome, less developed states have become parties to the binding of boundaries on ecological issues. Except Emerging countries help the world developing economically or all the way through technology transfer, Emerging countries are unlikely to be on the path to sustainable development.

As easy and efficient as economic incentive for ecological behavior is, there are a number of composite problems. For example, when there is improbability about it Benefits or control costs, taxes and trade licenses are no longer equal. Which one method is more efficient, which depends on the cost and cost of the benefits? (Weitzman, 1974).

(Futrell, 1994) stated that the organization of national and international ecological law is often contradictory and gradually in a way that allow most important environmental insults to go unrestricted by the law. For example, the U.S has laws on endanger species but not on bio diversity, and laws concerning to mineral extraction hold subsidies that often conflict with the goals of ecological law.

We lost the way of international protection of our environment the joint global because we have allowed our words to change to something else. We must change our words to insist once again on more effective legal restrictions to preserve "this dying planet" (Falk, 1971).

The RIO in 1992 Declaration at international level affirms the will of the international community to execute and favor the fortification and strong growth of a global environmental and tough economy. in the same way, in, 1986 the commission Report of Brundtland underline the significance that ecological safety has, following strong development. (Brundtland,1987).

Sustainable development and organization need the affiliation of all the nations of the globe, the only competent of ensuring a broad and well-organized economy. The protection and sustainable development of forests characterize a conception that has gained numerous

valences in recent years, because of the significance given to the forest by the participant in the collective development (Liagre, 1997).

The theory of sustainable development has made the social order conscientious and, in the identical time, be acquainted with, the role and significance of ecological factors as well as of the function and services the environment provides (Bortelmus, 1986).

HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT;

During the past, state governments have agreed irregular law to cover human health through ecological pollution. In about 80 AD, the governing body of Rome approved the law toward security the city's drinking and bathing without water. Within the fourteenth-14th century, European countries restricted dumping of Waste in waterway. In 1681, Queen Penn of Pennsylvania's British colonel, William Penn, structured that one acre forest cleared for settlement should be conserved in each five acres, and in the next century, Benjamin Franklin used to cover a variety of piles of garbage used the campaigns. During middle of the industrialized revolution 19th century, the British government approved the rules for reducing the environmental impact of coal burning and chemical formation. There were some international environmental agreements before the 20th century. Combined waterways mainly did not pay attention to border water, routing and fish rights and pollution and extra environmental issue. At the beginning of the 20th century, the conference was organized to protect commercially valuable species, which was involved in bird protection convention for 12 signed by European Governors (1902). Convention (11/11) for the protection of protection and protection completed the United States, Japan, Russia and Britain. And the protection of Edge Birds (1916), the U.S and the U.K (from Canada) reached Mexico and later in 1936.

In 1930, in, Egypt, Belgium South Africa, Italy, Portugal, Sudan and the UK agree to consultation relief to protect fonts in their natural status, which protected natural creatures and plants in Africa through countrywide parks and stores. France and Spain have signed, but has never confirmed it, and Tanzania officially agreed to it in 1962. In 1939, the India Accord was accused, in the documentation of the parts in which "trophy" was prohibited for any animal is described in the contract. At the beginning of the 1960s, the ecosystem in the West became significant political and academic group. Investigators in the America revised a wide range of real and potential environmental risks of a passionate test of the Royal Corps

of Silence Spring (1962), Chlorinated Hydrocarbon's insecticide and their use of environmental damage due to their use. Later in the decade, the US government passed several environmental laws, including waste, water and air smog and addressed the safeguard of risk group and made an ecological protection organization to detect their observance. This new environmental laws have significantly improved the role of state government in the region left for state and local regulatory. After World War II, with increasing rapid industrialization in Japan, in some areas with exposure to industrial chemicals in human food chains. For instance, in the city of Minamata, after eating industrial waste fish, a large number of mercury was affected by toxic. At the beginning of the 1960s, the Japanese government started considering the comprehensive organization strategy, in 1967; Japan made the globally comprehensive law for controlling environmental pollution. Minamata was not released until the end of the 20th century. In the fourth four countries adopted the international importance of the agreement in 1971, especially in the form of Water Fowl Habitats, which was usually identified as the Ramsar conference of Iran, which is signed. There are about 100 parties in the 1975 agreement. It was necessary that all countries should nominate minimum one secure prison land area, and it recognized the major role in maintaining environmental balance. After the UN Conference on the Human Environment held in Stockholm in 1972, the United Nations established the UN Environment Program (UNEP) as the world's largest international environmental organization. Although UNEP oversees several modern day agreements, there is no power to ban or enforce non-parties. Nevertheless, a series of important conferences was created directly, including the dumping of garbage or other substances (1972) and International Conference on International Trade and Risk International Trade (Wildlife) (1973) Maintenance Restoration Agreement Prior to the Stockholm Conference, the European countries were generally slow to implement the legal standards for environmental protection - although the exceptions there existed in the year 1968, the safety of England's rural areas was approved. In October 1972, after some months of the UN convention, European Community announced that the aim of economic expansion would be to maintain environmental balance. The European branch's executive branch developed the first year of its primary environmental program, and then the European countries were at the top of the environmental policy. For example, in Germany, at the beginning of the early 1980s public protection of environmental safeguard dramatically

changed when it came to know that many German forests were destroyed by its rains. The Green Party, founded in 1980, was first represented in Benedict (National Parliament) in 1983 and later campaigned for tough environmental regulations. By the end of the 20th century, the party joined the alliance government and was answerable for the development and implementation of Germany's wide ecological policies. A group, Germany, Denmark and Holland - as a famous "Green Troika" recognized itself as an important geography in the environmental law.

During the 1980s, the "Trans-Border Effect" of environmental pollution in many countries was discussed on many international environmental conferences. The effect of 1986 accident in the nuclear power plant was particularly important in Ukraine, after Chernobyl (after Soviet Union). At the bottom of pollution, steps were taken to restrict consumption of milk, milk, meat and Vegetable to the European countries. In Austria, radiation marks were found in cow milk with cow milk. As a direct result of Chernobyl's disaster, two international agreements - both early initialing and containment of nuclear accident were held in 1986 with an emergency accident or radiological emergency. Draft was created in case of a nuclear accident. In the next decade, a conference in Atomic Security (1994) has encouraged countries to adopt basic standards for safe operation on nuclear security plants.

Often there are several statistical data about the environmental impact of human activities, and scientific uncertainty often complicates the construction and implementation of environmental laws and regulations, especially to promote global standards for international conventions. In the attempt consequently, such rules and regulations are generally quite flexible to adjust scientific understanding and technical capabilities. For example, for the protection of Ozone Layer (1985), Vienna Convention did not take necessary measures to avoid the effects of ozone deficiency, it was not necessary to sign human health and environmental identification, nor To mention it The things that they thought of harming the Ozone layer were thinking. Similarly, Climate Change Framework Convention, or Global Warming Convention, in 1992, Rio de Janeiro (who is popularly known as "Earth's direction") in Rio De Janeiro, jointly organized 178 countries. Was it for The "Green House" caused global warming to reduce gas emissions?

In 1995, the international government on climate change is set up by the Global Climate Organization and UNEP to study the temperature changes in the earth, concludes that

"evidence is equal to the human impact on the global scale." The evidence of the global warming incident, the report was wrong to rely on the insufficient data by some critics, to eliminate the environmental impact of global warming and use the unrealistic model of environmental change. Two years later, Kyoto, in Japan, a conference sign for the Climate Change Framework Convention adopted Kyoto Protocol which was bound to the expense of developed countries. The protocol engages in expanding trading to developing countries to meet their expense goals. Its market mechanism involves the sale of "Emission Allowance units", which is earned when the developed country has failed to get its expenses to reduce the cost-effective costs. In developing countries, developing countries can get extra reduction units of energy efficiently (for example, clean development machinery). Since its authority, Protocol faced strong opposition from some countries, especially the United States, which was being confirmed.

ENVIRONMENTAL LAW

International environmental law responds sensitively to these two, possibly opposing trends, such as the need for globalization on the one hand, and the needs of developing states on the other. Environmental law is that the assortment of laws, rules, agreements and customary law that governs however humans act with their atmosphere. The aim of environmental law is to guard the environment and make rules for the way individuals will use natural resources. Environmental laws not solely aim to safeguard the atmosphere from damage, however they conjointly confirm World Health Organization will use natural resources and on what terms. Laws could regulate pollution, the employment of natural resources, forest protection, mineral harvest and animal and fish populations. The principles, policies, instructions and regulations are applied and implemented by local, national or international institutions so that human treatment of the non-human world can be regulated. The vast area encompasses a wide range of issues in diverse legal environments, such as the state law for the return of bottles in the United States, regulatory standards for emissions from coal-fired power plants in Germany, to create a "great wall" green "in China initiative a refuge to protect Beijing from the sand storm and international treaties for the protection of biological diversity and the ozone sphere. During the second half of the 20th century, the environmental law, developed from a modest range of public health regulations, protects both human health and inhuman nature in a universally recognized independent region.

Most environmental laws fall into a general category of command and control"; these laws generally include three elements: (1) identify a type of activity harmful to the environment, (2) apply specific conditions or standards to that activity, and (3) prohibit forms of activity that do not meet the conditions or standards imposed. . The Federal Water Pollution Control Act of the United States (1972), for example, "discharges" of "pollutants" governs the "navigable water of the United States." The three words are defined in the law and in the rules of the agency and identify the type as a whole. The activity harmful to the environment is subject to regulation. In 1983, Germany approved a National Emission Controlled, in which the specific air emission thresholds were determined environmental laws prohibit regulated activities that do not meet the conditions or standards Mentioned above. Many people "deliberately" violate such norms.

The most obvious forms of regulated activity include the actual discharge of pollutants into the environment (e.g. air, water and groundwater contamination). However, environmental laws also control activities that create a significant risk of discharging harmful pollutants (e.g. transport of hazardous waste, sale of insecticides and logging). For actual discharge, environmental laws generally determine specific limitations of acceptable contamination; For those activities that create the risk of discharge, the environmental law generally establishes management practices to reduce that risk.

The rules obligatory on the original substances usually approach in two types: (1) ecological or environmental standards, which treat highest regulation of pollution and (2) Extension, or exterior, quality, which controls the amount of pollution or disorders in any "source" environment. The most widespread environmental laws apply to equally environmental standards and exit values and try to manage their use of environmentally-friendly goals. The purpose of the environment can be numeric or narrative. Judgmental goals define a certain illness (for example, carbon monoxide of every micro meter per micro meter per eight hours). Statistical standards require that the water or air body is suitable for any particular use (for example, swimming). Methods for risk management activities are diverse and tourism specific. The United States Resources and Maintenance Act (1991), for instance, requires a depression pad contained in which hazardous waste is stored or stored, and the United States Petroleum Pollution Act (1990) is called All oil tankers can be two- way in operating US water at a certain size adage.

Another type of activity organized by the command of command and control is harmful business for the environment. The most developed rules are in the Wildlife business. For example, in World Life and Flora (CITES, 1973), which control international trade, for example, allows a conference for risk species, which may be affected by business. They are: Once a plant or animal species. It is dangerous to describe, the country is generally bound to limit restrictions on import or export of such nature, except for specific limited circumstances. In 1989, his involvement in the list of African elephants' preserved species effectively influenced trade in African elephants effectively, which was later banned by Kenya and ECC. At this time, the United States banned the trade in African elephants under an Act of Federal Elephant (1978), African elephants were involved in the list of dangerous species. Despite these initiatives, some countries did not ban the Import of diamonds (i.e. Japan) or refused to limit exports of orange (such as Botswana, Namibia, South Africa and Zimbabwe), and of deep complaints and smugglers had to face Risk.

ENVIRONMENTAL EVALUATION MANDATES

Environmental evaluation management is another important source of environmental law. Such orders typically do three things: (1) Identification or capacity of possible environmental impact, which reflects a reflection for consideration of reflective, (2) determining specific goals and (3) requirements for evaluation with the evaluation process proceeding as a real action or the decision to increase the future process will be considered. Contrary to command and control rules, this can limit the environment directly to the discharge.

Let's take the example of United States National Environmental Policy Act (1969) requires "the preparation of an environmental declaration that affects a large federal action of the environmental environment." In this statement, the environmental impact of the proposed action should be analyzed and considered as a series. The 1969 Constitutional Environmental aspects were set up under the Act to "nominate" the nominated "wait" for the environmental standards, the council's environmental standards, regulations and regulations for federal agencies to wait for. It was needed Preferred options will be preferred before proceeding. Similarly, the European Union (EU) needs two types of projects to assess the environmental impact assessment. Incomplete "projects in attachment" (for example, thermal power plants, oil refineries and 300 megawatts of heat tobacco), it is generally needed, and "connected

projects II" diagnosis chemical industry. The environmental impact of activities such as food, textile, leather, wood and paper, where only "member countries believe their needs are needed." Evaluation should be made directly and indirectly; landscape and conversation among plants, soil, water, air, environment and them.

ECONOMIC INCENTIVES;

Using financial resources to encourage environmental safety is a popular form of ecological law. Such promotions contain tax on pollution, subsidy and clean methods for technology, and creation of markets for environmental protection or pollution. For example, Denmark, Netherlands and Sweden apply tax on the cost of carbon dioxide, and the EU has decided whether these taxes should be applied to reset new changes. Pollution legislation passed in the United States of America, in 1972, provided subsidy to local government to improve waste visibly. In 1980, the new government, created by the National Government, affected by national pollution, caused by industrialized pollution in the New Canal Falls in New York, , has formed the Federal "Space", which uses general income and petroleum raw materials, raw oil tax was done and pollution with common corporate income dangerous substance to clean more than 1,000 sites. Since, in the 1990s, "Traditional subsidy projects" have been implemented in the United States, companies have been allowed to produce specific pollution rates for pollution or to produce and sell legal rights. In 1990 Clean Air Act, the most complete and complex, fossil fuel was designed to reduce total sulfur dioxide emissions of electric plants. According to supporters, the program will provide monetary rewards to the cleaner vegetation, which can put up for sale unnecessary loans in the marketplace and allow dirty plants to live in business, while they become cleaner technology. (Weitzman, 1974) stated that as simple and effective as economic incentives for environmental treatment are, there it is There are a number of complex problems. For example, when there is uncertainty about it Benefits or control costs, taxes and trade licenses are no longer equal. Which one method is more efficient, and depends on the cost and cost of the benefits.

These problems contains the opportunity that other non-economic objectives are important (such as equity and organizational simplicity), political limitations, high monitoring costs and other technological restrictions (Hahn and Stavins, 1992).

ENVIRONMENTAL COMPLIANCE AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT;

Compliance is the biggest challenge for the effectiveness of environmental treaties. However, they may try to implement compliance through mechanisms in the form of a treaty; such measures generally have limited utility, since countries that comply with the treaty are reluctant to implement the restrictions required for the treaty. Or it can be incapable. In general, the threat of sanctions is less important than most prospects for most countries in violating their international obligations and at the risk of having a significant loss in the international community. It is difficult to establish application mechanisms that are not restrictions, generally because they have to understand the important aspects of their national sovereignty for foreign or international organizations of the countries. Therefore, in most agreements, the application of the law is considered as an internal problem, an approach that efficiently allow each state to define compliance, in the way that best serves its national interests. Despite this difficulty, the importance of international environmental treaties and agreements is likely to increase as international environmental problems become more intense.

Many areas of international ecological law are not fully formed. While international agreements have helped to make laws or regulations to implement some types of activities dangerous to the environment in a more or less consistent manner in different countries, but may vary in the therapeutic methods applicable for such other activities. Because in most cases, damage due to activities harmful to the environment cannot be included within national borders, because due to the lack of continuity in the law, such situations have arisen, in which some countries have legal activities. As a result, there is a reason invalid or unacceptable level of environmental damage in neighboring countries.

In 1990, With the implementation of free trade agreements, this problem was particularly tough. For example, North America's Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA), which resulted in a massive ownership of McDurassas, the factories of the United States and Mexican corporations and worked in Mexico, with 60 US Mail (100km) Mexico. The internal border because the Mexican government is not due to lack of resources and political intent for lack of the country's environmental laws, rural people can be able to use dangerous area danger, often the most dangerous waste on the ground or directly in the canal. Drowning it was sent to the U.S. that he took it to the area. Prior to the adoption of the NAFTA in 1992, it is likely

to connect with the nominated "Party Agreement" of the Leader Talks, which promises environmental cooperation between the signed states. Meanwhile, there was opposition on the clear agreement between Europe, the open trade agreement and environmental destruction, which created the EU and extended its jurisdictions.

CONCLUSION

The paper reviewed the history and development of environmental laws with respect to economic growth and then sustainable development. Economic law and policies are not responsive and in most cases it is inappropriate to address domestic environmental issues. However, when dealing with cross-border environmental issues, it plays a role in promoting international cooperation and to punish non-compliance of agreement done by parties. For a generation, governments around the world have pledged sustainable development in the form of local programs and projects. Despite these efforts, decades of scientific observation suggest that the world is not close to environmental sustainability and, in many cases; the situation is only getting worse. Environmental protection concern has been increased globally in the recent decades. Issues such as climate change, ozone depletion, and the elimination of biological diversity are the result of international awareness of the problems facing the planet. Further, it is also recognized that if effective solutions are to be found for these problems, the states will need to work together more internationally. However, it is also acknowledged that many states suppress their own social and economic concerns, and that they have neither the resources nor the capabilities with which to deal with such global issues. International trade negotiations under World Trade Organization will devote substantial attention to protectionism and trade effects associated with environmental regulations.

REFERENCES

- [1] Africa International Programs". Environmental Protection Agency. Retrieved October 18, 2012.
- [2] AECEN". www.aecen.org Archived from the original on 2015-09-06. Retrieved 2015-08-27.
- [3] Developing States and International Environmental Law: The Importance of Differentiated Responsibilities by (Duncan French, 2008)
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0020589300063958>

- [4] Environment and Trade as Partners in Sustainable Development: A Commentary
Edith Brown Weiss Georgetown University Law Center,
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- [5] Fuentes, X. International Environmental Agreements: Politics, Law and Economics (2002) 2: 109. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1020990026398>.
- [6] Free Trade, Regulatory Competition and the Autonomous Market Fallacy Joel R. Paul UC Hastings College of the Law, paulj@uchastings.edu. University of California.
- [7] Hastings College of the Law UC Hastings Scholarship Repository Faculty Scholarship 1995.
- [8] Falk, Richard A. (1971). This Endangered Planet: Prospects and Proposals for Human Survival. New York: Random House.
- [9] Human Rights in Natural Resource Development: Public Participation in the Sustainable Development of Mining and Energy Resources. Edited by Donald M.
- [10] Hahn, Robert W, and Robert N Stavins. “[Economic Incentives for Environmental Protection: Integrating Theory and Practice](#).” *The American Economic Review* 82 (1992): 464–468.
- [11] Institutional Misfits: The GATT, the ICJ & Trade Environment Disputes Jeffrey L. Dunoff Temple University School of Law. Michigan Journal of International Law Volume 15 | Issue 4 1994.
- [12] Liagre, J.(1997). La foretET le droit.DroitForestieretDroit General Paris: Ed. La Baule.
- [13] LucretiaDogaru / Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences 93 (2013) 1344 – 1348.
- [14] OECD Economic Studies No. 23, Winter 1994 A SURVEY OF THE TRADE AND ENVIRONMENT NEXUS: GLOBAL DIMENSIONS by JohnBeghin, David Roland-Holst and Dominique van der Mensbrughe.
- [15] Sustainable Development and Human Rights: An Integrated Conception by Dominic McGoldrick<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0020589300059704P> published online by Cambridge University Press: 17 January 2008.

- [16] United Nations Conference on Environment and Development. (1992). Rio Declaration on Environment and Development, A/CONF.151/26/Rev.1 (Vol. 1).
- [17] United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development, Report of the Secretary-General. (2010). U.N. Doc. A/CONF.216/PC/7.
- [18] United Nations Environment Programme. (1989). Register of International Treaties, U.N. Doc. UNEP/GC.15/Inf.2
- [19] United Nations Environment Programme (2007). Global Environment Outlook: Environment for Development.
- [20] Weitzman, M. L. (1974) "Prices vs. Quantities," The Review of Economic Studies, XLI, 477-99.
- [21] Zillman, Alastair Lucas and Pring, George (Rock) in OUP Catalogue from Oxford University Press.

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